

COMPARISON OF LIVER ENZYMES DERANGEMENT IN DENGUE FEVER, DENGUE HEMORRHAGIC FEVER AND DENGUE SHOCK SYNDROME

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19590098>

Keywords

Dengue fever, Dengue hemorrhagic fever, dengue shock syndrome, Hepatic dysfunction.

Article History

Received: 10 May 2025

Accepted: 15 June 2025

Published: 13 July 2025

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the prevalence of hepatic dysfunction in adults with dengue fever and to compare liver parameters in patients with dengue fever, dengue hemorrhagic fever, and dengue shock syndrome.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Nishtar Hospital, Multan, from August 2024 to January 2025. We included 193 patients aged 18-65 years, of either gender, admitted with a diagnosis of dengue fever. Baseline characteristics, including age, gender, and duration of illness was recorded. Grading of illness (DF/DHF/DSS) was determined by the attending consultant on admission. Enzymatic assays (ALT, AST, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, and LDH) using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer and PT / INR were performed.

Results: The study participants' baseline characteristics were as followed: The average age was 36.5±11.7 years. Regarding gender, 118 participants (61.1%) were male, and 75 (38.9%) were female. The mean illness duration was 4.9±1.7 days. In terms of illness severity, 110 individuals (59.9%) were diagnosed with Dengue Fever (DF), 66 (34.2%) with Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and 17 (8.8%) with Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS). The occurrence of hepatic dysfunction increased with disease severity: affecting 15.5% of DF, 27.3% of DHF, and 41.1% of DSS patients (P = 0.02).

Conclusion: Hepatic dysfunction frequently occurs in patients with dengue infection. Therefore, these patients should be closely monitored and managed to prevent and identify any complications early.

INTRODUCTION:

Dengue virus (DENV) is a flavivirus transmitted by mosquitoes, with four distinct serotypes labeled 1 through 4 that are commonly found in regions where the disease is endemic. The majority of DENV infections do not produce symptoms. When symptoms do appear, they can range from mild dengue fever to severe conditions such as dengue hemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome.^{1,2}

Dengue fever remains endemic across over 100 countries in tropical and subtropical regions. Although largely confined to these warm climates, recent data shows the disease is spreading to new areas, including parts of Southern Europe and the United States.³ In recent years, the global number of DENV infections has surged dramatically. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reports that dengue accounts for approximately

400 million cases annually, resulting in around 40,000 fatalities.⁴

It is anticipated that dengue transmission will become more intense in regions where the disease is already endemic. Additionally, factors such as climate change and the rise in international travel could facilitate the spread of the infection to European and U.S. areas currently minimally impacted.⁵

The liver enzyme levels usually increase and reach a peak around the ninth day after the onset of symptoms, and in 3 weeks return to normal levels. The cause of hepatic involvement in dengue infection is unclear, but it may be due to the direct effect of viral load or to an impaired host immune response against the virus. Liver involvement is now recognized as a major factor influencing prognosis, with 60-90% of hospitalized patients exhibiting some degree of liver dysfunction.^{6,7} Manifestations may include minor increases in liver enzymes without symptoms, or progress to severe hepatic failure. Patients commonly experience enlarged liver (hepatomegaly), abdominal discomfort, yellowing of the skin or eyes (jaundice), and raised levels of AST and ALT.^{8,9}

The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of hepatic dysfunction in adults with dengue fever and to compare liver parameters in patients with dengue fever, dengue hemorrhagic fever, and dengue shock syndrome.

METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Nishtar Hospital, Multan, from August 2024 to January 2025. We included 193 patients aged 18-65 years, of either gender, admitted with a diagnosis of dengue fever. We excluded patients with a history and medical record suggestive of ischemic heart disease, heart failure, positive viral hepatitis serology, chronic liver disease, malaria, and typhoid fever. Written consent was obtained from all patients.

Baseline characteristics, including age, gender, and duration of illness was recorded. Grading of illness (DF/DHF/DSS) was determined by the attending consultant on admission. The following criteria were used to categorize DF, DHF and DSS.

Dengue Fever (DF): Patients who exhibit a history of fever for less than ten days and present with at least two of the following symptoms—retro-orbital pain, headache, joint pain, muscle pain, rash, bleeding issues, thrombocytopenia (platelet count below 100,000 per mm³), and leukopenia (white blood cell count below 4,000 per mm³)—and who test positive for dengue through serological methods such as IgM detection or NS-1 antigen testing via enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), are classified as dengue fever cases.

Dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF): DHF diagnosis was established when evidence of plasma leakage was observed, either through a hematocrit increase exceeding 20% from baseline or through fluid accumulation, such as a pleural effusion or ascites, confirmed by ultrasound, in individuals with Dengue infection. Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) was identified in confirmed Dengue cases that exhibited a sudden and weak pulse alongside a narrow pulse pressure of less than 20 mmHg, or experienced hypotension.

A venous blood sample of 5 mL was drawn from each patient into a plain tube on admission. All blood samples were sent for the estimation of all liver parameters.

Enzymatic assays (ALT, AST, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, and LDH) using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer and PT / INR were performed. The following criteria were used to diagnose hepatic dysfunction. Presence of any one or more of the following in patients with confirmed dengue was labelled as hepatic dysfunction: ALT >50 U/L, AST >140 U/L, ALP >420 U/L, LDH >580 U/L, serum bilirubin > 2 mg/dL, prothrombin time >20 seconds, and/or INR >1.2.

The data was analyzed through SPSS version 23. Liver parameters were compared among DF/DHF/DSS using ANOVA, while the Chi-square test was used to compare the frequency of hepatic dysfunction between DF, DHF, and DSS patients; p-values < 0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS:

The study participants' baseline characteristics were as followed: The average age was 36.5 years, with a standard deviation of 11.7 years.

Regarding gender, 118 participants (61.1%) were male, and 75 (38.9%) were female. The mean illness duration was 4.9 days, with a standard deviation of 1.7 days. In terms of illness severity, 110 individuals (59.9%) were diagnosed with Dengue Fever (DF), 66 (34.2%) with Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and 17 (8.8%) with Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) [Table 1].

A comparison of liver parameters among patients with Dengue Fever (DF), Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) shows significant differences in several biochemical markers. The average alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels were 53.2 ± 45.3 U/L in DF patients, 104.5 ± 110.3 U/L in DHF patients, and much higher at 359.1 ± 315.7 U/L in DSS patients (F ratio: 50.33, $P < 0.0001$). Similarly, aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels increased with disease severity: 85.3 ± 60.8 U/L in DF, 165.4 ± 140.8 U/L in DHF, and 765.8 ± 420.8 U/L in DSS (F ratio: 143.3, $P < 0.0001$). Alkaline phosphatase was elevated in DSS

(131.7 ± 97.1 U/L) compared to DF (71.4 ± 32.9 U/L) and DHF (85.3 ± 60.5 U/L) (F ratio: 10.31, $P < 0.0001$). Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels increased with disease severity: 189.5 ± 30.4 U/L in DF, 267.2 ± 64.9 U/L in DHF, and 356.3 ± 80.5 U/L in DSS (F ratio: 71.07, $P < 0.0001$). Bilirubin levels were highest in DSS (1.1 ± 0.9 mg/dL), followed by DHF (0.8 ± 0.5 mg/dL) and DF (0.6 ± 0.2 mg/dL), with significant differences among groups (F ratio: 12.59, $P < 0.0001$). Prothrombin time (PT) was notably longer in DHF (25.3 ± 7.7 sec) compared to DF (11.5 ± 1.3 sec) and DSS (15.6 ± 3.2 sec) (F ratio: 178.0, $P < 0.0001$). The international normalized ratio (INR) followed a similar pattern, being highest in DHF (1.6 ± 0.7), then DSS (1.4 ± 0.5), and DF (0.9 ± 0.1) (F ratio: 54.23, $P < 0.0001$). The occurrence of hepatic dysfunction increased with disease severity: affecting 15.5% of DF, 27.3% of DHF, and 41.1% of DSS patients ($P = 0.02$). These results demonstrate a clear link between dengue severity and changes in liver function parameters. [Table 2].

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age (Years)	36.5±11.7
Gender (%)	
Male	118 (61.1%)
Female	75 (38.9%)
Duration of Illness (days)	4.9±1.7
Grade of Illness (%)	
DF	110 (59.9%)
DHF	66 (34.2%)
DSS	17 (8.8%)

Table 2. Comparison of Liver parameters in DF, DHF and DSS Patients.

Variable	DF (N=110)	DHF (N=66)	DSS (17)	F ratio	P-value
ALT (U/L)	53.2±45.3	104.5±110.3	359.1±315.7	50.33	<0.0001
AST (U/L)	85.3±60.8	165.4±140.8	765.8±420.8	143.3	<0.0001
Alkaline Phosphatase (U/L)	71.4±32.9	85.3±60.5	131.7±97.1	10.31	<0.0001
LDH (U/L)	189.5±30.4	267.2±64.9	356.3±80.5	71.07	<0.0001
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.6±0.2	0.8±0.5	1.1±0.9	12.59	<0.0001
PT (sec)	11.5±1.3	25.3±7.7	15.6±3.2	178.0	<0.0001

INR	0.9±0.1	1.6±0.7	1.4±0.5	54.23	<0.0001
Hepatic Dysfunction (%)	17 (15.5%)	18 (27.3%)	7 (41.1%)	---	0.02

DISCUSSION:

Our research showed that the highest prevalence was among patients with dengue fever at 59.9%, followed by those with warning signs at 34.2%, and severe dengue cases at 8.8%. Of these, 61.1% were male and 38.9% female, giving a male-to-female ratio of 1.6:1. This gender distribution aligns with other studies. For example, a study in Brazil found 53.25% of affected patients were male, versus 46.75% female.¹⁰ In 1980, Kaplan's epidemiological research in Mexico indicated a higher incidence among females. Differences in gender patterns across studies are often due to varying hypotheses; hospital-based studies may not fully represent the entire affected population, as they only include those seeking medical care. Kaplan suggested indoor daytime transmission as a factor for higher female infection rates, while Goh and Ooi argued that because *Aedes* mosquitoes—main vectors—breed mainly outdoors, this led to lower infection rates among females.^{11, 12}

Dengue fever can cause a wide spectrum of liver issues, ranging from mild increases in liver enzymes to severe, potentially fatal liver failure. The liver damage related to dengue arises from various factors, including the virus's direct toxicity to cells, immune responses, and decreased blood flow. Post-mortem studies of affected individuals reveal changes like small fat deposits within liver cells, cell death, overgrowth and damage of Kupffer cells, presence of Councilman bodies, and infiltration of inflammatory cells. Immunohistochemical tests show infiltration by CD4+ and CD8+ T lymphocytes and increased interferon-gamma levels, indicating Th1 immune activation. Moreover, dengue can damage endothelial cells of venules or sinusoids, impairing microcirculation and causing liver cell ischemia, even with normal blood pressure.^{6, 7, 13, 14} In endemic areas, dengue may worsen existing chronic liver diseases, potentially triggering acute liver deterioration.

Shah S et al enrolled 100 symptomatic dengue serology positive patients. Raised alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate

aminotransferase (AST) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were seen in 45%, 45% and 28% cases respectively. Mean levels of ALT, AST and ALP were 119.69±134.73, 189.06±217.38 and 105.56±43.33 in DF, 610.56±750.44, 1788.33±3336.34 and 150.44±83.95 in DHF, and 425.80±163.88, 579.60±171.65 and 120.60±28.10 in DSS (p <0.05).¹⁵ A study included 220 adult with dengue fever. There were 164 diagnosed as DF, 52 as DHF and 4 as DSS. About 65% of the patients were males and 35% were females. The mean age of the patients was 33.219 years. Fifty-seven percent (57%) of total patients developed liver dysfunction. Liver function profile analysis showed that liver dysfunction developed more in DF than in DHF (38.15 vs. 18.6%).¹⁶

The investigation took place at a single tertiary care hospital in Multan without excluding patients based on prior or concurrent use of hepatotoxic medications. Patients with hepatitis A and E could not be definitively ruled out, as tests for these conditions were costly and not routinely performed. Including patients with secondary infections may also introduce bias into the results, highlighting the need for further research to determine the cause of liver involvement in these cases. It is crucial to assess additional liver damage markers like prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, albumin, and total protein levels. Further exploration is needed to understand how dengue infection influences these parameters and whether there is a link to elevated transaminase levels.

CONCLUSION:

Hepatic dysfunction frequently occurs in patients with dengue infection. Therefore, these patients should be closely monitored and managed to prevent and identify any complications early. Additionally, in dengue-endemic areas, all febrile patients should avoid hepatotoxic drugs to prevent further liver damage if they have dengue.

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